

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

ABOUT STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF A SUBSTANCE CONTAINING DEFECTS OR INCLUSIONS

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Abstract

The idea of the relative degree of order in a substance with structural defects or inclusions is introduced. The suitability of this quantity for comparing the level of order in different material samples or in various regions of a heterogeneous material is shown. In development of the works of prof. A. Herega discusses the possibility of clarifying the terminology used when describing the structure.

Keywords: structure, relative degree of orderliness, Lyapunov functional, Kullback-Leibler distance, Klimontovich's S-theorem, integral characteristic of structure

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern natural science, the concept of structure is among the basic ones. It can be understood both as “a model description in which order is established in the distribution of characteristic quantities” [1], and as “a state arising as a result of the coherent (consistent) behavior of a large number of particles” [2]. Definitions of this type do not pretend to be complete and cannot be exhaustive: structure as a fundamental concept is defined by a list of properties. Such descriptions contain both quantitative characteristics (lattice constants, atomic diameters, coordination numbers, binding energies, etc.) and qualitative ones (presence or absence of long-range order, type of lattice, type of symmetry, etc.).

Numerous studies devoted to specifying the dependence of material properties on structure, as a rule, contain photographs of surfaces or sections that make the difference in the structure of samples with different properties clear. Realizing the importance of the dependence of the properties of a substance on the structure, understanding that, in fact, properties are a manifestation of structure, the authors of many articles provide verbal descriptions of photographs, using intuitive terms – “heterogeneous distribution of cracks”, “structured placement of filler”, “complex configuration of the location of defects”, and others – but which do not include clear definitions, calculation algorithms, or a quantitative component.

In this regard, it is appropriate to have a characteristic that would make it possible to quantitatively assess the level of order in the structure from photographs. One of the quantities that gives such an opportunity is the relative degree of order in the structure of matter, determined from images [3], – a quantitative characteristic that is calculated using an operable algorithm based on the idea of the entropy of an information system.

2. RELATIVE DEGREE OF ORDER OF IMAGES

As is known, the semantic and visual content of an

image significantly depends on the characteristics of the observer, his psychological attitude, method of viewing and other circumstances [4, 5]; but formation of objective characteristics, methods of their definition and measurement presupposes the fulfillment of certain requirements, and, above all, the formalization of the image [6-8].

Let's consider the issue of comparing two images as information objects, and determine the relative degree of their order (RDO) [3].

When determining a relative characteristic, the question of the correctness of comparison of objects necessarily arises. In the case of images, an adequate comparison is possible by analogy with how it is carried out in the Gibbs theorem on the entropy of equilibrium and arbitrary states [9-11]. Gibbs entropy is determined, as is known, by the average value of the logarithm of the equilibrium distribution function of the complete set of coordinates and momenta of the particles of the system. Comparison of the entropy values of equilibrium and nonequilibrium states can be made only at the same values of average energies, thereby limiting the set of nonequilibrium states. The normalization conditions for equilibrium and nonequilibrium distribution functions must also be the same [9-11].

Let's imagine a computer image as an array of pixels made in 256 shades of gray. The average amount of gray level (GL) per pixel should be the same in the compared images. To fulfill this condition, the distribution density functions $f_1(i)$ and $f_2(i)$ of gray level values in image pixels are reconstructed from the array data, and then according to the formula

$$\tilde{f}_2(i) = f_2(i) \left[\frac{\sum_{i=0}^{255} f_1(i)}{\sum_{i=0}^{255} f_2(i)} \right] \quad (1)$$

one of them is renormalized.

In [3] it is shown (I-theorem) that a measure of the relative degree of ordering of two equal-sized images with the same value of the average gray level is the Lyapunov functional

$$S_1 - \tilde{S}_2 = - \sum_{i=0}^{255} [f_1(i) \ln f_1(i) - \tilde{f}_2(i) \ln \tilde{f}_2(i)] = - \sum_{i=0}^{255} [f_1(i) (\ln f_1(i) / \tilde{f}_2(i))]. \quad (2)$$

Note that a similar result is known in information theory: the Kullback-Leibler distance is a measure of the difference in probability distributions [12, 13], and in the theory of open systems: Klimontovich's S-theorem is a criterion for the relative degree of ordering of nonequilibrium states of open systems [14, 15].

3. COMPUTER IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHOD

A grayscale image is programmatically converted into a one-dimensional data array that contains numerical gray-level values in each pixel of the original image. When forming an array, boustrophedon is used as a rule for traversing the image (Greek "the way of the bull" – a type of writing with a variable direction of lines: odd lines are written from right to left, even lines – vice versa). This is due to the fact that possible options for estimating the relative degree of order provided in the computer program are associated not only with the analysis of individual pixels, but also with comparison of GL of neighboring pixels: by difference or ratio, by the absolute value of this difference, and others.

The algorithm for leveling the integral GL is based, as noted, on the renormalization of the gray distribution density function in pixels. One of the compared images is selected as a reference, and to achieve an equal GL, either stretch-compress the distribution function of the second image according to formula (1), or its displacement along the axis on which the gray

level value is plotted. If requirements exist that minimize the possibility of image modification, then to achieve equal average GL, the distribution functions of both images are shifted in opposite directions [3].

Taking into account the above-described capabilities of the program for varying array processing modes, for each pair of compared images, 32 variants of the Lyapunov functional can be obtained. According to our data, the most sensitive, as a rule, are estimates made by the value of the gray level in pixels.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let's consider the results of two experimental studies [16] and [17].

In [16], using interference microscopy methods, a study of the structure and properties of oxide coatings deposited on the surface of a deformable aluminum alloy V95T1 was carried out, which is usually used for the manufacture of compression structures. Authors of the article [16] found, in particular, that coatings obtained using different technologies have elastic moduli and microhardness that differ by 8 and 15%, respectively (Table 1).

According to our data, the relative degree of order, calculated from intensity maps of the surface of the samples (Fig. 1), shows that sample A is more ordered in the sense described above: RDO is 0.26. This means that with increasing order of the coating structure, its microhardness increases, and its elastic modulus decreases (see Table 1).

Fig. 1. Surface intensity maps of samples A and B [16].

Table 1.

Mechanical characteristics of coatings (fragment of the table from [16]).

Parameter	Sample A	Sample B
Microhardness, GPa	10.65 ± 1.6	9.26 ± 2.12
Modulus of elasticity, GPa	157.2 ± 12.16	170.1 ± 12.4

In [17] the dependence of the mechanical properties of rubbers containing carbon black on the "uniformity of filler distribution in the material" was studied. Author [17] believes that "in samples 1 and 3 (see Fig. 2), the distribution can be considered uniform, while in the second, clusters of clusters forming separate groups are observed". He also believes that "the more heterogeneous the distribution and the larger the cluster sizes, the stronger the filler-filler interaction, the stress field is more inhomogeneous and there are more

hysteresis losses under cyclic loading". "From this point of view, the second sample has the worst mechanical characteristics" [17].

Firstly, we note that in the cited paper [17] author uses overtly subjective statements. For example, of the cluster system, he writing "can be considered uniform distribution", and does not allow itself the expression "uniform distribution". Secondly, you should pay attention to the fact that the author of paper does not use any quantitative characteristics.

Fig. 2. Photographs of the surfaces of filled rubber obtained using an atomic force microscope [17].

Our proposed method for calculating the RDO of surface photographs showed that the second sample is more ordered than the first ($\Delta S = 4.683$) and third ($\Delta S = 4.752$). Taking into account the experimental results [17], it is clear that with an increase in the order of the structure of carbon clusters in rubber, its mechanical properties deteriorate.

5. CONCLUSION

The relative degree of order can be considered as an objective quantitative integral characteristic of the structure of physical bodies, which is an alternative to subjective descriptive concepts such as “structuring” and “heterogeneity”, and allows quantitative characterization of material properties.

In addition, the possibility of introducing “absolute” orderliness into consideration is obvious. To determine it, you need to select the zero of the scale: this can be the ordering of the image created by a random number generator with a uniform distribution, or, on the contrary, the complete orderliness of the “black square”.

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